

MICROMYSETS FOUND IN THE TREE OF SOME PINE FORESTS IN AZERBAIJAN

Abdullaeva Sh.

Ph.d.

teacher

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6912382>**Abstract**

The main purpose of the work was to study the micromycetes that cause the destruction of trees growing in the pine forests of Azerbaijan. The aim was to study the effects of fungi on trees and to clarify ways to combat them. In general, it was concluded that the methods of combating the fungus are very different, but not successful.

Keywords: Azerbaijani forests; fungal diseases; micromycetes.

INTRODUCTION

The research was conducted in the pine forests of some regions of Azerbaijan. The purpose was to investigate the cause of the mass destruction of pine trees. In recent years, in the pine forests of Azerbaijan, the decay and even destruction of the organs of trees for unknown reasons has been observed. When studying the reason for this, it became clear that the role of fungi, especially micromycetes, is more important in the destruction of trees. During the study, a large number of diseases were observed in the trees. More information about the disease is given below.

Root rot. The study will first discuss root rot, one of the diseases of the pine tree. Due to this disease, the pine tree begins to change the color of its leaves and slowly, but surely, the plant withers until it finally dies. The disease is caused by a fungus *Phytophthora cinnamoni*, and if this happens, if it is in a bowl, you can try to remove it, change the whole soil and apply antifungal treatment. But experts know that it is very difficult to save the plant (look picture 1).

In fact, if this happens, it is recommended to cut the root before affecting other branches.

Picture 1

Rust is a disease found in many pine trees. The causative agent of the disease is the fungus *Puccinia*. The disease manifests itself in the tree with many small black spots on the leaves and twigs.

Drying of branches - the death of individual branches and the entire crown, the top and the crown. The disease can occur as a result of infection of the branches, root rot, lack of soil moisture.

Cancer or edema-infection occurs as a result of local thickening of the branches, trunk and root (swollen cancer), mechanical damage or settlement of the flower parasite.

Cancer ulcer - a progressive ulcer that grows every year, sometimes surrounded by discharge.

Stain disease. We can say that this is the most serious pine disease. Because this disease will cause the tree to grow less and grow weaker. The disease is more pronounced in the summer, but may already be infected in the winter. Leaf and conifer staining. Stains come in various shapes, sizes and colors due to fungal, bacterial, viral infections, gas poisoning, chemicals and exposure to sunlight. Infection with this disease weakens the growth process, the leaves dry out, the resistance of shoots and twigs to infectious diseases and non-parasitic factors. Signs that the pine tree is suffering from this disease are: the leaves turn yellow (look picture 2), some even cling to twigs and manifest themselves with pink pustules. All this is done by a fungus (*Rousselian pseudometry*), and the only solution in these cases is to cut all the infected branches from the place where the symptoms begin to appear and burn them immediately. Regardless of the signs of tree disease, the leaves of the tree should also be cut. Because fungal spores have already spread to the surface organs of the tree. As we know, fungal spores have the ability to spread rapidly.

Picture 2

Infection, frostbite, etc. can also be caused by non-parasitic factors. The ulcer is a door through which wood-breaking fungi enter. As a result of infection of resinous plants, the resin breaks down the paths and the flow of resin.

Necrosis is the death of individual organs and tissues. In the case of necrosis of the branches and trunk, a longitudinal dead bark strip accumulates in the upper layer of the branch and trunk. They can also be caused by fungal and non-infectious causes. Infectious necrosis can cause epithelium.

Mummification is a disease associated with the formation of skeletal cells in fruits and seeds or their transformation into fungal stroma.

Deformation - a change in the shape of an organ or part of a plant. Infectious twisting of leaves, deformation of fruits, bending of shoots and branches are observed.

Bending of seedlings - pulling branches, spreading them on the ground and destroying them. Such spread of all species occurs as a result of infection, sunburn, contact with sand. It destroys crops and reduces the quality of seedlings and planting material.

Yellowing of conifers and leaves - discoloration due to destruction of the plant or infection of plant parts. It is caused by infectious and non-infectious factors.

To overcome this, in the case of pine, you need to apply a mixture of sulfur, zineb, maneb and mancozeb, as it is most effective. Now it will take some time for the plant to recover.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sampling was carried out systematically (route) and unsystematically, and the samples taken were analyzed according to the known mycological methods relevant to the purpose of the work. Samples were taken mainly from the surface organs of plants, ie leaves, stems, flowers and fruits, and this work was carried out on a seasonal basis.

In general, about 1,000 samples of pine trees in Azerbaijani forests were taken during the research. The

development of the samples was analyzed in the laboratories of the mycology department of the Institute of Microbiology of ANAS.

The probable part of the samples taken by fungi, ie micromycetes, was either washed and transferred to the nutrient medium, or the process itself was transferred to the nutrient medium to obtain a pure culture.

During the separation of macromycetes, the fruiting body (MC) formed by the fungus in the plant, ie basidioma, was used. The extracted MC was used to obtain a pure culture in the laboratory after certification, which is possible in the field. For this purpose, small particles (0.2-0.5x0.2-0.5 cm) are cut from the hymenophore part of the MC with a sterilized lancet and transferred to a nutrient medium, and as the colony is formed, it is transferred to a new medium and the process continues until a homogeneous colony is obtained.

RESULTS

As a result of the research, the names of micromycetes that cause the destruction of trees in the pine forests of Azerbaijan and the diseases they cause, the prevalence were determined (look table 1). Methods of combating fungal diseases were investigated.

Table 1

Fungal diseases observed in pine forests of Azerbaijan and their prevalence (%)

N	Name of the disease	The causative agent of the disease	The degree of spread
1	Brown trunk rot	<i>I.hispidus</i>	12,6-56,7
2	Brown trunk rot	<i>F.pinicola</i>	7,8-12,8
	Brown root rot	<i>F.pini</i>	2,1-4,3
3	White body rot	<i>F.fomentarius</i> <i>G.applanatum</i>	7,8-11,2
4	Stain	<i>A.alternata</i> , <i>C.microsora</i> . <i>L.fumago</i> , <i>Ph.opuli</i> <i>S.populi</i> , <i>Ph.ulmi</i> <i>Rh.salicinum</i> .	1,2-3,9
5	Pas	<i>M.populnea</i> <i>M.salicina</i>	1,7-3,4
6	Flour dew	<i>E.alphitoides</i>	2,3-5,4
7	Necrosis	<i>N.cinnabarina</i> <i>C.quercina</i>	0,7-1,4

To combat this fungus, it is best to remove all dry or yellowish areas, as well as fallen leaves, and burn them immediately. In addition, you need to apply cork products and two more actions:

- Water the leaves without moistening
- Spray once every two weeks in the spring to reduce the chances of the fungus appearing (or reappearing).

It is not normally seen in well-maintained box trees, but is seen in trees that are weaker due to maintenance deficiencies or overcrowding, or because other trees suffer from tree diseases or pests.

To eliminate this, in addition to cutting the most affected parts, it is necessary to remove and burn the leaves that may be on the ground. You also need to apply an antifungal mixture to completely eliminate it.

References:

1. Horst K. R. Westcott's Plant Disease Handbook. Eighth Edition. New York: Springer Science, 2013, 826 c.
2. <http://www.agroatlas.spb.ru>
3. <http://www.mycobank.org/Mycotaxo.aspx>
4. Seifert K., Rossman A. How to describe a new fungal species// IMA Fungus, 2010, v. 1, № 2, p.109–116
5. Tomoshevich M., Kirichenko N., Holmes K., Kenis M. Foliar fungal pathogens of European woody plants in Siberia: an early warning of potential threats?// Forest Pathology, 2013, vol. 43, № 5, p. 345–359.